

EFFECTIVENESS OF ANIMAL AND PLANT EXTRACTS ON HEMATOLOGY AND HISTOPATHOLOGY OF MICE EXPOSED TO CIGARETTE SMOKE: A REVIEW

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In 2018, the Indonesian Ministry of Health reported that Indonesia was listed as the country with the third highest number of smokers in the world after China and India. Smoking is known to be a contributor to lung, cardiovascular and several other chronic diseases (Kemenkes RI, 2018). Several studies have also reported that smoking is closely related to a number of dangerous diseases such as coronary artery disease (CAD) (Ambrose *et al.*, 2004), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (Alexandrov *et al.*, 2016), cancer in human organ systems and decreased reproductive health (Covac *et al.*, 2015). This disease that occurs due to smoking is caused by the chemical compounds contained in cigarette smoke. It is reported that there are at least 72 chemical compounds that are toxic to humans. Therefore, smoking not only has a bad impact on the smoker, but also on the people around him who participate (Ueno *et al.*, 2015). Exposure to cigarette smoke also feels the impact. Exposure to free radicals from cigarette smoke will certainly cause physiological changes in body. Therefore, studies related to the effectiveness of various animal or plant extracts are an interesting topic for further research in order to look for antioxidant candidates that are able to counteract exposure to free radicals from cigarette smoke so that they can maintain the physiological condition of the body. Furthermore, this study is an interesting topic to research because it could pave the way for the development of natural and perhaps more affordable alternative therapies to protect and repair the damage caused by cigarette smoke. Apart from that, the use of animal and plant extracts as a source of active ingredients in the health sector shows innovation in the sustainable use of biological resources and has high economic value, considering that the animal and vegetable sources used are environmentally friendly (Danes *et al.*, 2022).

All types of plants actually always release secondary metabolites, which then have potential bioactivity that can be utilized in various treatments. These secondary metabolites are very useful for humanity because they have broad therapeutic activity. Secondary metabolites produced by plants include alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids and steroids (Roy *et al.*, 2022). One of the secondary metabolites that is quite popular in plants is flavonoids. This flavonoid compound is reported to have potential as an antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimutagenic, antiallergic, antiviral and anticarcinogenic (Adegroba *et al.*, 2006). Plants are a source of medicine because natural extracts from plants are believed to have no side effects. Currently, countries in Asia and Africa use more than 80% of plants as a source of medicines (Rastogi *et al.*, 2015). The antioxidant potential of flavonoid compounds from plants can be an antioxidant that fights free radicals from exposure to cigarette smoke. Many studies related to this have been carried out both *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Among the plant extracts that have been tested include extracts from the *Eugenia uniflora* plant (Santoso *et al.*, 2020), and also from katuk leaf plants, cherry fruit, black cumin oil, juwet fruit, lime, etc. (Zulkarnain *et al.*, 2020).

Apart from plants, animals are also a source of medicines that are widely used in the medical world. Almost the same as the reasons for using plants. Extracts from animals are believed to have no side effects (Alves & Rosa, 2005). Since ancient times, animals and their various body organs have been used as a source of medicine. The use of medicines derived from animals is increasingly known as zotherapy. In India almost 15-20 percent of Ayurvedic medicine is based on ingredients of animal origin. In the State of Bahia, in northeastern Brazil, more than 180 medicinal animals have been recorded (Costa Neto, 2004). As for antioxidant sources, in contrast to antioxidants from plants, in animals the source of antioxidants can come from amino acids or protein. Examples of antioxidant proteins include ovotransferrin and fosvitin. The antioxidant potential in animals is currently a widely researched study (M. Anda & Howell, 2015).

One animal extract that has benefits as a good drug candidate for antioxidants is Black Soldier Fly (*Hermetia Illucens*). Maggot BSF is one of the insects whose nutritional content and characteristics are currently being widely studied (Rahayu *et al.*, 2023). The latest research from Nurinayah proves that BSF larvae extract contains natural antioxidants *in vitro* and *in silico* which can prevent oxidative stress by activating Nrf2 and Keap1 signaling (Nurinayah, 2023). Nrf2 activation functions as a protective mechanism against cellular damage caused by free radicals, which can be observed as tissue repair or protection in histopathological studies as well as modulation and protection of blood components in hematological studies. Through its role in regulating antioxidant and detoxification responses, Nrf2/Keap1 signaling contributes to the maintenance of cellular homeostasis and tissue integrity (Nguyen *et al.*, 2009). *In vitro* research conducted by Firmansyah and Abduh (2019) reported that BSF larval protein hydrolyzate has antioxidant activity. Apart from its potential as an antioxidant, BSF extract also has good anti-inflammatory activity (Afriani *et al.*, 2023). The use of BSF animal extracts as a source of active ingredients in the health sector shows innovation in the sustainable use of biological resources and has high economic value, considering that BSF larvae are easy to cultivate and environmentally friendly (Rehman *et al.*, 2023).

Seeing the antioxidant potential in BSF larvae, it is important to carry out research regarding the effectiveness of BSF extract on the hematological and histopathological profiles of mice exposed to cigarette smoke. If BSF extract proves effective, it could pave the way for the development of natural and perhaps more affordable alternative therapies to protect and repair the damage caused by cigarette smoke. Apart from that, the use of BSF larvae as a source of active ingredients in the health sector shows innovation in the sustainable use of biological resources and has high economic value, considering that BSF larvae are easy to cultivate and environmentally friendly (Riolo *et al.*, 2023). The use of BSF as a drug candidate for the future from an ecological aspect will not lead to extinction because this animal actually actively reproduces and is capable of producing many offspring (Solovan *et al.*, 2004).

REFERENCES

- Aderogba, M. A., Ogundaini, A. O., & Eloff, J. N. 2006. Isolation of Two Flavonoids From *Bauhinia Monandra* (Kurz) Leaves and Their Antioxidative Effects. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 3(4), 59-65.
- Afriani Y, **Rahayu R**, **Santoso P**. 2023. Fatty Acid and Hematology Profile of Black Soldier Fly (*Hermetia Illucens* L.) Maggot Oil in Wound Healing. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*. 2023;39(2): 429-433
- Alexandrov, L. B., Ju, Y. S., Haase, K., Van Loo, P., Martincorena, I., Nik-Zainal, S., ... & Stratton, M. R. 2016. Mutational Signatures Associated With Tobacco Smoking in Human Cancer. *Science Journal*, 354(6312), 618-622.
- Alves, R. R., & Rosa, I. L. 2005. Why Study The Use of Animal Products In Traditional Medicines?. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*, 1,
- Ambrose, J. A., & Barua, R. S. 2004. The Pathophysiology of Cigarette Smoking and Cardiovascular Disease: an update. *Journal of the American college of cardiology*, 43(10), 1731-1737.
- Costa-Neto, E. M. 2004. Implications And Applications Of Folk Zotherapy In The State Of Bahia, Northeastern Brazil. *Sustainable Development*, 12(3), 161-174. 1-5.
- Danesh, H., Ziamajidi, N., Mesbah-Namin, S. A., Nafisi, N., & Abbasalipourkabir, R. 2022. Association Between Oxidative Stress Parameters and Hematological Indices in Breast Cancer Patients. *International Journal of Breast Cancer*, 2022.
- Firmansyah, M., & Abduh, M. Y. 2019. Production of protein hydrolysate containing antioxidant activity from *Hermetia illucens*. *Heliyon Journal*, 5(6).
- Kementrian Kesehatan RI. 2018. Situasi Umum Konsumsi Tembakau Di Indonesia.
- Kovac, J. R., Khanna, A., & Lipshultz, L. I. 2015. The Effects of Cigarette Smoking on Male Fertility. *Journal Postgraduate Medicine*, 127(3), 338-341.
- M. Anda, Howell N. 2015. Peptida Bioaktif Antioksidan dan Penghambat ACE Dari Protein Kuning Telur Yang Dimurnikan. *Int. J.Mol. Sains*. 2015; 16 :29161–29178.
- Nguyen, T., Nioi, P., & Pickett, C. B. (2009). The Nrf2-antioxidant response element signaling pathway and its activation by oxidative stress. *Journal of biological chemistry*, 284(20), 13291-13295.
- Nurinayah, I. 2023. Aktivitas Antioksidan In Vitro dan Regulasi Persinyalan Antioksidan In Silico oleh Ekstrak Larva Black Soldier Fly (*Hermetia illucens*). Skripsi : Institut Pertanian Bogor.
- Rahayu, R.**, Utari, S. D., **Santoso, P.**, Zaini, E., & Jessica, A. 2024. Effectiveness Of Black Soldier Fly (*Hermetia illucens*) Prepupa Oil Emulgel For Burn Wound Recovery. *Tropical Journal of Natural Product Research*, 8(3), 6589-6593.
- Rastogi, S., Pandey, M. K., Prakash, J., Sharma, A., & Singh, G. N. 2015. Veterinary Herbal Medicines in India. *Pharmacognosy Reviews*, 9(18), 155.
- Rehman, K. U., Hollah, C., Wiesotzki, K., Rehman, R. U., Rehman, A. U., Zhang, J., ... & Aganovic, K. 2023. Black soldier fly, *Hermetia illucens* as a potential innovative and environmentally friendly tool for organic waste management: A mini-review. *Waste Management & Research*, 41(1), 81-97.

- Riolo, K., Rotondo, A., La Torre, G. L., Marino, Y., Franco, G. A., Crupi, R., ... & Giannetto, A. 2023. Cytoprotective and antioxidant effects of hydrolysates from black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*). *Antioxidants*, 12(2), 519.
- Roy, A., Khan, A., Ahmad, I., Alghamdi, S., Rajab, B. S., Babalghith, A. O., ... & Islam, M. R. 2022. Flavonoids a bioactive compound from medicinal plants and its therapeutic applications. *BioMed Research International*, 2022(1), 5445291.
- Santoso, P.**, Cahyaningsih, E., & Darmayanti, G. A. P. E. 2020. Pengaruh pemberian ekstrak n-butanol buah dewandaru (*Eugenia uniflora* L.) terhadap gambaran histopatologi paru mencit (*Mus musculus*) jantan yang terpapar asap rokok. *Jurnal Ilmiah Medicamento*, 6(1).
- Solovan A, Paulmurugan R, Wilsanand V, Ranjith Sing AJA. Traditional therapeutic uses of animals among tribal population of Tamil Nadu. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*. 2004;3:206–207.
- Ueno, M., Ohara, S., Sawada, N., Inoue, M., Tsugane, S., & Kawaguchi, Y. 2015. The Association of Active and Secondhand Smoking with Oral Health in Adults: Japan Public Health Center-Based Study. *Tobacco Induced Diseases Journal*, 13, 1-9.
- Zulkarnain, Z., Amrullah, S. H., Rukmana, R., Nurman, N., & Alir, R. F. 2020. Keanekaragaman Flora Kandidat Antioksidan dalam Memperbaiki Kualitas Spermatozoa yang Telah Terpapar Asap Rokok. In *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Biologi (Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 36-40)*.